

<http://zoobank.org/urn:lsid:zoobank.org:pub:B6AD0545-C88F-4356-94FB-1E8601BFADDA>
DOI: 10.24412/2226-0773-2024-13-8-712-718
EDN: TMFTHX

Taxonomic notes on longhorned beetles with the descriptions of several new taxa (Coleoptera, Cerambycidae). Part 2

M.A. Lazarev

Free Economic Society of Russia, Department of Scientifics Conferences and All-Russian Projects
Tverskaya str., 22a, Moscow 125009 Russia
e-mail: humanityspace@gmail.com, cerambycidae@bk.ru

Key words: Coleoptera, Cerambycidae, taxonomy, zoogeography, new subgenus, new synonyms, restored name, new status, new name.

Abstract: Many newly published taxonomy modifications are discussed. Several taxonomy news are proposed. Nine subspecies names of *Polyarthron pectinicornе* (Fabricius, 1793) used by Sama (2023) are accepted as valid. Taxonomy of *Clytus rhamnii* Germar, 1817 is discussed. *Parmena* (*Pilosoparmena* **subgen. nov.**), type species: *Parmena pudescens* (Dalman, 1817) is proposed. *Phytoecia* (*Danilevskia* Lazarev, 2024, type species *Saperda molybdaena* Dalman, 1817) [not *Danilevskia* Kuznetsov, 1970, type species *D. silvana* Kuznetsov, 1970, Lepidoptera] must be replaced by *Ph.* (*Danilevskovia* **nom. nov.**). New synonyms are proposed: *Tetrops praeustus praeustus* (Linnaeus, 1758) = *T. peterkai* Scořepa, 2020, **syn. nov.** = *T. praetermitus* Sláma, 2020, **syn. nov.**

1. According to Sama (2023: 53), *Polyarthron pectinicornе* (Fabricius, 1793) is “a single very variable species”. He did not show any infraspecific taxon of *P. pectinicornе* in the synopsis of the family (p. 21). Never the less the areas of 4 subspecies were illustrated by him in the map of North Africa (Fig. 175). Many subspecies were divided in smaller taxa, which cannot be accepted by modern Zoological Code (ICZN, 1999) as infrasubspecific. Now I try to save for nomenclature Sama’s taxonomy and propose to regard his subspecies names as the names of subspecies groups. So, the general system of the species must look as:

1. Group-*pectinicornе*

1. Subspecies: *P. p. pectinicornе* (Fabricius, 1793: 251) - the marginal west of the group area: Senegal.

2. Subspecies: *P. p. faurebigueti* Pic, 1898a: 165 - north-west of the group area - Mali (from Akjoujt, Tombouctou to Sokoto).

3. Subspecies: *P. p. gaillardi* (Lameere, 1912: 231)

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- marginal east of the group area - Niger, Chad (to Ennedi).

2. Group-jolyi

1. Subspecies: *P. p. jolyi* Pic, 1895: ccclxxxv (= *filali* Kocher, 1956: 124) - north of the group area - Morocco, Alger (Tafilalet, Adrar, Ghardaia)

2. Subspecies: *P. p. lothei* (Villiers, 1946: 35) (= *saharensis* Pic, 1898b: 27) - south-east of the group area - Alger (In Salah, Ajjers)

3. Subspecies: *P. p. reymondi* Kocher, 1956: 124 - marginal west of the group area - Morocco (Dra).

3. Group-fairmairei

1. Subspecies: *P. p. fairmairei* Pic, 1893a: 110 (= *barbarum* Fairmaire & Coquerel, 1866: 67 [HN]) - north of group area - Alger, Libya (Ghadames, Touggourt, Biskra, Sousse)

2. Subspecies: *P. p. chatanayi* (Lameere, 1915: 59) - south of group area - Libya (Fezzan), Chad (Tibesti), Niger (Bilma)

4. Group-desvauxii

1. Subspecies: *P. p. desvauxii* Fairmaire, 1868: 499 (= *moissoni*, Pic, 1893b: cclx, = *pici* Lameere, 1912: 229, = *separatum* Pic, 1901: 15) - north of the species area - Alger (Aïn Sefra, Bou-Saada).

2. Several good series of *Clytus rhamni* Germar, 1817 from different countries are available at author's disposal: France, Italy, Albania, Greece, Bulgaria, Ukraine, Moldavia, Russia, Armenia, Azerbaijan, Georgia. Each series is characterized by high level of individual variability, but statistically several characters demonstrate good geographical peculiarities. Western population (France, Italy, Albania, Greece) mostly consists of specimens with all femora dark and light antenna. Such populations could be attributed to the nominative subspecies - *C. rhamni rhamni* Germar, 1817 described from Italy (= *bellieri* Gautier des Cottes, 1862 - Corsica). The most part of the species area (Bulgaria, Ukraine, Moldavia, Russia, Armenia, Azerbaijan, Georgia.) is represented by populations with red antennae, red anterior legs and partly darkened posterior femora, middle femora dark or light. All such populations can unite in a single subspecies - *C. rh. temesiensis* (Germar, 1824) (Transsylvania). Villiers (1978) wrongly described antennal color of *C. rh. rhamni* and *C. rh. temesiensis* as apically dark.

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3. *Rosalia syriaca* Pic, 1895 was restored by Özdikmen (2024) as “stat. nov”, though it was published by Pic (1900).

4. *Calchaenesthes* Kraatz, 1863 (type species *Callidium oblongomaculatum* Guérin-Méneville, 1844) is accepted now as valid, but in fact it was a synonym of *Calchaenistes* Schaum, 1862: 102 (type species *Callidium nogeli* Frivaldszky von Frivald, 1845 - monotypy). So, the oldest name must be regarded as nomen oblitum.

5. *Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) gashtarovi* Sama G., Dascalu M. & Pesarini C. 2010 is downgraded to subspecies rank: *Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) catenatum gashtarovi* Sama, Dascălu & Pesarini, 2010, **stat. nov.**

6. *Dorcadion divisum* v. *thebesianum* Pic, 1942: 1 (“Thèbes” - Greece) recently published as *Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) catenatum catenatum* Walzl, 1838 - [Turkey] (= *thebesianum* Pic, 1942) must be regarded as *Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) catenatum thebesianum* Pic, 1942 **nom. rest.**

7. *Parmena (Pilosoparmena subgen. nov.)*, type species: *Parmena pudescens* (Dalman, 1817). Prothorax and elytra with numerous erect setae. Elytra and prothorax in the nominative subgenus without long erect setae.

Etymology. The name *Pilosoparmena* (feminine) consists of Latin *pilosa* (hairy) and old genus name *Parmena*.

New subgenus includes 13 species:

balearica balearica Vives, 1998

balearica minoricensis Vives, 1998

bicincta Küster, 1849

breuningi Vives, 1979

cruciata Pic, 1912

= *schrammi* Pic, 1945

lukati Sama, 1994

mutilloides Sabbadini & Pesarini, 1992

novaki Sama, 1997

pilosa pilosa Brullé, 1832

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= *hirsuta* Küster, 1846
pilosa inclusa Mulsant, 1862
= *dahlia* Mulsant, 1862: 245
pubescens Dalman, 1817
= *algerica* Laporte, 1840
= *minuta* Pic, 1891
slamai Sama, 1986
soldatii Cocquempot, 2020
solieri Mulsant, 1839
= *lanzai* Sama, 1985
= *pilosa* Solier, 1835 [HN]
subpubescens Hellrigl, 1971

Parmena (s. str.) includes 11 species:

aurora Danilevsky, 1980
balteus Linnaeus, 1767: 1067 (*Cerambyx*)
= *balteata* Fabricius, 1793: 262 (*Cerambyx*) – wrong subsequent spelling
= *fasciata* Villers, 1789: 239 (*Cerambyx*)
= *gauthieri* Stöcklein, 1940
batumiensis Danilevsky, 2023
bialookii Danilevsky, 2017
europaea Danilevsky, 2017
istanbulensis Danilevsky & Hizal, 2017
lodosi Özdikmen & Tezcan, 2020
meregallii Sama, 1984
pontocircassica Danilevsky & Miroshnikov, 1985
striatopunctata Sama, 1994
[*samai* Özdikmen, 2021] - unavailable name
[*sericata* Sama, 1996] - unavailable name
unifasciata Rossi, 1790: 147 (*Lamia*)

8. *Phytoecia* (*Danilevskia* Lazarev, 2024, type species *Saperda molybdaena* Dalman, 1817) [not *Danilevskia* Kuznetsov, 1970, type species *D. silvana* Kuznetsov, 1970, Lepidoptera] must be replaced by *Ph. (Danilevskovia* **nom. nov.**).

9. *Tetrops praeustus praeustus* (Linnaeus, 1758) = *T. peterkai* Scořepa, 2020, **syn. nov.** = *T. praetermitus* Sláma, 2020, **syn. nov.**
The morphological differences described by the authors of each name are completely insignificant.

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10. A syntype of *Agapanthia verecunda* Chevrolat, 1882 was published by Kasatkin (2020) as “male, lectotype”, though the lectotype was never formally designated. So, the depicted male (“Syria, in montibus Drusarum. A.D. Coye capta et data.”) from Muséum national d’Histoire naturelle (ex. collection C. Bowring-Chevrolat, Paris, France) is designated here as lectotype.

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Received: 15.09.2024

Accepted: 25.10.2024